

Research Article**Different approaches for improvement of acclimatization step of in vitro micropropagated local Juglansregia L. genotypes in Uzbekistan**Guljakhon Eshbekova¹, Bakhtiyor Kodirov² and Zafar Ismailov¹**Article Info**

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Abstract.

Tissue culture of Persian walnut (*Juglansregia* L.) is considered difficult compare to other crops. In this research, different methods, including seed starters and polystyrene cups, as well as pot mixture in different ratios were used to increase the efficiency of the acclimatization stage after microclonal propagation of local varieties and forms. According to the results of the research, the survival rate in all genotypes: Ideal variety, PDM23 form and 202YaKT form was higher, respectively, 58.3%, 65.8%, 29.2 % when seed starters or polystyrene cups were used in the peat: biohumus: perlite mixture in the ratio of 1:2:1. Also, the success of the acclimatization stage depends on the genotype, and the 202YaKT form showed a low performance compared to other genotypes.

Keywords: *Juglansregia* L., microclonal propagation, acclimatization, local variety, Ideal variety, PDM23 form, 202YaKT form.

Introduction.

Today, one of the best methods for mass propagation of walnut (*Juglansregia* L.) in order to establish orchards on an industrial scale is in vitro microclonal propagation [1,2,3]. However, the rooting stage of that process is considered more difficult; the acclimatization stage also has some limitations. The results of the research showed that the quality of in vitro micro shoots, formation of roots, the characteristics of stomata on the leaves, the presence of sufficiently healthy leaves, and the genotype are important factors for the successful acclimatization stage [4,5,6].

Low water capacity in the multiplication and rooting stages of in vitro explants also affected the survival rate in the next adaptation stage [6]. In addition, the substrate used for acclimatization and adherence to the standard rules of temperature and humidity during the process are considered to be the most important rules [7]. Several studies have been conducted to increase the efficiency of the acclimatization stage, mainly related to changing the temperature and humidity for different periods of time. At the initial stage, direct sunlight and low temperature ($<16\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the growth chamber caused a decrease in survival rate [8,9].

After the in vitro explants transferred to the ex-vitro stage, it was observed that the relative humidity was higher than 80-90% during the first two weeks, and when it was gradually reduced to 60% during the next 2-3 weeks, the condition of the leaves was well preserved in the seedlings [10]. When peat, perlite and vermiculite in 1:1:1 ratio [11] and peat and vermiculite in 1:1 ratio [12] were used as substrate, 60.5% and 79.2% survival was observed respectively. In the course of research, it was found that the result of microclonal propagation of walnut, as well as the stage of acclimatization, depends on the genotype [13]. However, insufficient studies have been carried out on the composition and ratio of the substrate during the acclimatization stage. In this study, the results of the use of different substrates for the acclimatization of local walnut genotypes of Uzbekistan and the use of different methods to maintain high relative humidity for seedlings in the first two weeks are presented.

Materials and methods.

Plant Materials

Three Persian walnut (*J. regia* L.) genotypes were obtained from Scientific-research institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Wine-making (Uzbekistan): variety 'Ideal' (N41°36.157; E70°05.767) and 'Form

202YaKT' (N41°36.157; E70°05,767), 'Form PDM23' (N39°73.852; E66°73,381)[14,15]. Initial explants were taken from stem cuttings multiplied in vitro for at least 10 subcultures.

Multiplication.

Uninodal explants were cultured in Driver and Kuniyuki medium (DKW) [10] with 96 mg/L^{-1} Fe-EDDHA, supplemented with 1.5 mg/L^{-1} BAP, 0.01 mg/L^{-1} IBA, 30 g/L^{-1} sucrose, 0.4 mM phloroglucinol and gelled with 5.5 g/L^{-1} Agar. The pH was adjusted to 5.7 before autoclaving.

Root induction.

Explants of three genotypes collected during the multiplication phase were cultured in DKW medium, with 1/2 macronutrients and 96 mg/L^{-1} Fe-EDDHA, added with 3 mg/L^{-1} IBA, 30 g/L^{-1} sucrose, gelled with 5.5 g/L^{-1} Agar. The pH was adjusted to 5.7 before autoclaving.

Acclimatization.

To increase the efficiency of the acclimatization step, in vitro micropropagated explants were adapted to greenhouse conditions in 3 different ways:

1. Initially, rooted microshoots were planted in peat tablets (41 mm diameter) on open nursery trays and incubated in mini-greenhouses under controlled conditions (Fig.1 B,E). Mini greenhouses were covered with glass to maintain high relative humidity ($90\pm 2\%$). After the 3rd week, glass covers were removed slowly, in such a way that plants were acclimated step-by-step to a gradually-reduced humidity. In this stage a photoperiod of 16/8 h was used, with an average light intensity of 3500 lx; whereas temperature was $24\text{--}26\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. During the 4th week, surviving plants were transplanted to plastic cups (500 cm^3 , upper diameter 93 mm, lower diameter 55 mm, height 135 mm) with a two types of mixture (rate 1:1:1, 1:2:1) of peat, biohumus and perlite. Pots were placed in a greenhouse under normal conditions,

with oscillating temperatures and relative humidity ranging from 17 to 32 °C and from 45 to 75%, respectively, and an average maximum light intensity of 4600 lx. Plants were watered 1 to 2 times per week, depending on the weather and the state of the

substrate. When micropropagated plants were acclimatized (6th week), survival and quality of plants of each genotype from both culture media were counted, and the general state was annotated.

Figure 1.A,B,C-polystyrene cups, open nursery trays, seed starters used in experiments; D,E,F-Seedlings during acclimatization (initial two weeks) under the polystyrene cup, on open nursery trays, inside of seed starters.

2. Rooted microshoots were transferred directly to pots containing two different mixtures (500 cm³, upper diameter 93 mm, lower diameter 55 mm, height 135 mm) and covered with polystyrene cups (Fig.1 A,D). Through this, 95 ± 2% humidity was provided for seedlings. In the first 2 weeks, the cups

were not opened in order to ensure high humidity (95 ± 2%) for the plants under the polystyrene cups. Then, in the 3rd week, holes were opened in the upper part of the polystyrene cups, and in the 4th week, the polystyrene cups were removed. Then, pots

were placed in a greenhouse under normal conditions.

3. Rooted microshoots were planted in vitro peat tablets (41 mm diameter) and incubated in seed starter containers (Fig.1 C,F). In this case, the valves located in the lids were not opened in order to ensure high humidity (95 ± 2%) in the first 2 weeks. Then, in the 3rd week, the valves were opened, and in the 4th week, the transparent lids were opened. Then, pots were placed in a greenhouse under normal conditions.

Statistical analysis.

Statistical analysis was performed using Origin 8.6 software (Microcal Software Inc., Northampton, MA). Results were expressed as mean ± SE. All experiments were repeated three times and 120 plants were treated in each experiment.

Results and discussion.

Some authors reported that biohumus can be used instead of peat when growing plants in greenhouse conditions [16,17]. By adding biohumus to the pot mixture, seedlings can be fed in sufficient quantity.

Table 1.Survival rate of seedlings on different methods and ratio of potting mixture during acclimatization step.

Methods for improving efficiency of acclimatization	Survival rate of seedlings (%)					
	Ideal variety		PDM23 form		202YaKT form	
	1:1:1	1:2:1	1:1:1	1:2:1	1:1:1	1:2:1
Seed starters	46.7±2.5	54.2±2.6	51.7±2.4	65.8±2.3	19.1±0.8	29.2±1.8
Polysterine cups	48.3±1.9	58.3±2.8	56.7±3.1	60±1.8	NE	NE
Open nursery trays	25.8±1.2	31.7±1.6	22.5±1.3	37.5±1.1	NE	NE

Values in each column represent means ± SE.NE-non evaluated.

Also, it allows reducing the amount of greenhouse gas released when peat decomposes [18,19]. The results of the study showed that the survival rate of all three genotypes: Ideal variety, PDM23 form and 202YaKT form showed a high result in peat: biohumus: perlite mixture in the ratio 1:2:1 (58.3%, 65.8%, 29.2%, respectively).

It was found that the genotype is important in the microclonal propagation of walnut, as well as in the acclimatization stage [20,21]. Two of the 3 genotypes selected in this study, Ideal variety and form PDM23, showed successful performance at all stages, however, rooting and acclimatization index were relatively low in form 202YaKT (the highest acclimatization index was 29.2%).

In the first 2-3 weeks during the acclimatization stage, maintaining high humidity and protecting seedlings from various external environmental influences are important for the successful process [22,23]. For this reason, in order to maintain high humidity and increase the survival rate in the first weeks, seed starter containers, polystyrene cups were used and compared with seedlings planted in open nursery trays. There were significant differences on the survival rate of plantlets which acclimatized on open nursery trays and seedling starters, as well as under polystyrene cups. The survival rate of seedlings of the Ideal variety was 31.7% when acclimatized in nursery trays with 1:2:1 peat: biohumus: perlite mixture, and 58.3% when covered with polystyrene

cups. The survival rate of PDM23 form seedlings acclimatized in nursery trays was 37.5% in 1:2:1 peat: biohumus: perlite mixture, and 65.8% in seedling starter. Therefore, the use of different methods to ensure high humidity for seedlings during the acclimatization of seedlings propagated by the microclonal method may allow to increase the survival rate.

Conclusion.

To conclude, it is possible to use biohumus in the pot mixture to increase the efficiency of acclimatization stage of walnut microclonal propagation. It is also effective to use different methods, including seed starters or polystyrene cups, to ensure high humidity for seedlings during the first two weeks. Furthermore, the efficiency of the acclimatization stage highly depends on the genotype.

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